

Studying Healthcare in Rural India

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Abstract

In this note, the authors present some statistics of the evolution of rural health care studies over the years since India's independence.

Consider the following data points.

1. 1950-1960:359
2. 1960-1970:915
3. 1970-1980:4770
4. 1980-1990:12400
5. 1990-2000:17500
6. 2000-2010:52400
7. 2010-2020:104000

The above data points are plotted in the histogram of Figure 1. The histogram is obtained by doing a decade-wise search for “rural healthcare in India” in Google Scholar. The data shows a remarkable rise in studies of rural health care in India over the decades leading up to the 21st century, which appears to be the “knee” of the exponential.

To form a sharp contrast we do a similar search for rural United States. We obtain:

1. 1950-1960: 15800
2. 1960-1970: 16400
3. 1970-1980:16700
4. 1980-1990:17800
5. 1990-2000:18400
6. 2000-2010:18100
7. 2010-2020:18100

Figure 1: Studies of rural health care in India.

Figure 2: Studies of rural health care in the United States.

The data is shown in Figure 2. The data show a steady and high stream of scholarly work on health care in rural United States. A decade-by-decade comparison shows that in the new millennium, India has been the subject of more scholarly work on rural health care issues.